

Rights of the Christ's faithful

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God has created us in his own image and likeness and put the breath in our body. He created us to give glory to God and praise him by doing his will. He gave them free will. He gave some rights and obligations to every human being. Canon law recognizes these rights and obligations.

These rights and obligations we find in the second book called 'The People of God. This book of the code of Canon law is divided into three parts. They are 1. Christ's Faithful, 2. The Hierarchical Constitution of the Church and 3. Institutes of Consecrated Life and Societies of Apostolic Life. Most of the rights we find in the first part of the book. "There is a genuine equality of dignity and action among all of Christ's faithful" (C. 208; *LG* 32). All members of the church are now described as "Christ's Faithful." Right is an interest recognized and protected by the rule of law.

According to Cardinal Ottaviani "right" is meant an inviolable moral faculty of doing, omitting, or demanding something. Most people tend to speak of their rights in very broad terms. But there is a vast difference between my right to life which is the most fundamental of all human rights and my right to smoke.

The rights in the Church, as in civil society, are different in nature and kind. On the basis of their sources, rights in the Church can be grouped into six main categories: human or natural; ecclesial; ecclesiastical; communal or religious; civil and contractual.

Natural or Human Rights:

Human dignity proclaimed in the Code but as arising from human nature are:

The right of an association and assembly [C. 215]

The freedom of inquiry and expression in sacred sciences [C. 218]

The freedom from coercion in choosing one's state in life [C.219]

The right to reputation and privacy [C. 220]

The right to vindicate one's right in the proper forum and due process of law when using courts [C. 221]

These are only a few examples of human rights declared in the Code, but they are not creations of any positive law, for they preexist the law.

Ecclesial Rights

These are the direct consequences of baptism, and these, for example, are:

The right to the holiness of life [C. 210]

The right to participate in spreading the Gospel [C. 211]

The right to share in the sacramental life of the Church [C. 213]

The right to initiate and promote apostolic action [C. 216]

The right to a Christian education [C. 217]

Again, these rights are not granted by the disposition of the legislator but by the Christ himself who acts in the sacraments. The Church has the power to regulate the exercise of these rights for the common good, but their existence is from Christ himself.

Ecclesiastical Rights

These are direct consequences of ecclesiastical offices.

The functions especially entrusted to the Parish Priest [C. 530]

Juridic representation of the Parish and Administration of Parochial Goods [C. 532]

Parish Finance Council [C. 537]

The Church's Fundamental right to Judge [C. 1671].

Rights and obligations of Judicial Vicar and judges and Defender of Bond etc. [C. 1504, 1506, 1513, 1576 – 1587, 1601-1606, 1607-1613 etc.]

Communal or Religious Rights

Part third of the book concerns the religious profession, such as enclosure [C. 667], the obligation of the Institute to support the members [C. 670].

Civil

It deals with the canonization of civil law [C. 22]

Contractual

It emerges from the contract with the civil authority such as Lateran Treaty on 11th February 1929, Leasehold lands etc.

Let us enjoy the rights given by God

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